

INNOVATIVE NANOCARRIER FOR BRAIN DRUG DELIVERY: MECHANISTIC
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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18480121>**How to cite this Article:** P. Devaraj¹, S. Vanitha^{2*}, R. Sambathkumar³, S. Allimalarkodi⁴, and S. Revathi⁵ (2026). Innovative Nanocarrier For Brain Drug Delivery: Mechanistic Insights And Translational Challenges. European Journal of Pharmaceutical and Medical Research, 13(2), 346–356.

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Article Received on 05/01/2026

Article Revised on 25/01/2026

Article Published on 04/02/2026

ABSTRACT

The Blood brain barrier is a selective protective barrier that nearly all macromolecular therapies and more than ninety eight percent of small molecules cannot cross. The structure is maintained by the neurovascular unit, which is composed of endothelial cells, pericytes, and astrocytes joined by tight junctions that restrict paracellular transit. To address this issue, nanocarriers have demonstrated promise as efficient delivery systems for medications that target the brain. Liposomes, exosomes, polymeric nanoparticles, dendrimers, and biomimetic nanoparticles are the five primary categories of nanocarriers. Passive diffusion, carrier-mediated transport, receptor-mediated transcytosis, and adsorptive-mediated transcytosis are some of the methods by which these carriers can move through the blood-brain barrier. In actuality, they can be used to treat neurological disorders including Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease, strokes, brain tumours, and traumatic brain injury. Their effectiveness is mostly determined by their size, charge, shape, and surface modifications with specific ligands such as transferrin or polyethylene glycol. However, there are still problems with immunological clearance, instability, low penetration efficiency, and potential neurotoxicity. Future research will focus on improving nanocarrier design, increasing targeting specificity, and addressing regulatory issues in order to implement these innovative brain-targeted therapies.

KEYWORDS: Blood brain barrier, Nanocarrier, Mechanism, Neurological Disorders.**1. INTRODUCTION**

The microvasculature of the central nervous system is surrounded by the semi-permeable blood brain barrier (BBB). Tight junctions are extensively created in the capillaries by the wedged endothelial cells that border the inner channels. The barrier controls the movement of molecules between the vascular compartment and the brain, working alongside various receptors, transporters, efflux pumps, and other cellular components.^[1,2] The majority of blood-borne chemicals are prevented from entering the brain by an intact blood-brain barrier. However, it should be mentioned that in addition to protecting the brain, the BBB prevents entry to the brain for over 98% of small molecule medications and all macromolecular therapies.^[1] Neuronal dysfunction and degeneration might result from the CNS being invaded by toxins, pathogens, immune cells, or ion dysregulation if the BBB isn't there. Only passive diffusion of lipid-

soluble medications with molecular weights less than 400–600 Da is permitted by the narrow gap.^[3] Important pathways for the transfer of solute and nutrient molecules into the brain are found in the blood-brain barrier. Drugs can traverse the BBB through receptor-mediated transcytosis. The development of innovative techniques based on in-delivery drug-conjugated nanoparticles (NPs) has been the focus of research efforts.^[4] The BBB prevents big, hydrophilic molecules (>500 KDa) from entering and only permits tiny, lipophilic molecules to pass through.^[5] Drug delivery methods based on nanotechnology are being investigated as a solution to this problem. Usually ranging in size from 10 to 100 nm, nanoparticles (NPs) provide superior stability, minimal toxicity, controlled drug release, and increased BBB permeability. Numerous nanocarrier systems have demonstrated potential.^[6] Phospholipids and cholesterol combine to generate liposomes, which

are biocompatible, biodegradable, and frequently used to encapsulate active ingredients while reducing systemic toxicity.^[7,8] Because of their endogenous biological origins, exosomes have extended circulation, immunological evasion, improved biocompatibility, and source-dependent targeting.^[9] Polymeric nanoparticles (PNPs) demonstrate high drug-loading capacity, good stability, and enhanced penetration, making them versatile carriers.^[10] Dendrimers, with their symmetric and monodisperse architecture, provide possibilities for precise drug attachment and controlled delivery, though their synthesis can lead to heterogeneity.^[11] Biomimetic nanocarriers, inspired by cell membranes, further improve targeting, prolong circulation, and evade immune surveillance by integrating membrane proteins and carbohydrates.^[12,13] The effectiveness of these nanocarriers depends on physicochemical properties such as particle size, morphology, surface charge, composition, and functionalization with ligands like transferrin, insulin, peptides, or polyethylene glycol. These strategies collectively goal to improve BBB permeability, enabling novel therapeutic approaches for treating CNS disorders.^[14]

2. STRUCTURE OF BLOOD BRAIN BARRIER

Paul Ehrlich made the first discovery of the BBB, and Edwin Goldmann established its existence. The BBB is a large, dynamic, multicellular, semi-permeable membrane that separates the central nervous system from the

blood's foreign materials.^[1] The BBB blocks blood cells, fluid components, and pathogens from entering the brain by creating a tightly regulated neural vascular unit (NVU) consisting of vascular cells, pericytes, astrocytes, and tightly bound junctions. It further regulates homeostasis by regulating the motion of substances into and out of the brain's nervous system.^[15] Managing the homeostasis of the brain's central nervous system depends upon the blood-brain barriers, an active, multilayered structure that governs the movement of substances through the blood stream and the brain. Its main anatomical component involves brain capillary endothelial cells. In contrast with peripheral endothelia, these cells have only a few of pinocytotic vesicles and close interconnections (TJs) that seal the para cell gap.^[16] The neurovascular unit is a functional unit made up of endothelial cells, which are surrounded by a basement membrane and interact tightly with astrocyte end-feet and pericytes.^[17] While active efflux transporters like P-glycoprotein form a metabolic barrier by removing potentially harmful compounds, tight junctions, which are composed of proteins like occludin and claudins, create a physical barrier. The healthy operation of neurons and the protection of the brain from poisons and infections depend on this extremely selective and protected environment.^[18] Figure 1 represents the structure of blood brain barrier.

Figure 1: Structure of blood brain barrier.

3. TYPES OF BRAIN TARGETED NANOCARRIERS

3.1 Liposome

One of the most researched and therapeutically advanced method for delivering specifics to the brain is liposomes. These phospholipid- grounded vesicles are extremely biocompatible and able of containing specifics that prefer fat or water. Size, face charge, and lipid composition.^[19] To increase blood-brain barrier penetration, surface modification is necessary. While certain targeting ligands encourage receptor-mediated absorption, PEGylation

increases circulation duration by reducing protein adhesion and immune detection. Studies have demonstrated that by interacting with endothelial cells, glutathione-PEG liposomal formulations significantly increase brain absorption. however, the effectiveness of these formulations is heavily determined by the lipid composition. Compared to neutral or anionic formulations, cationic liposomes show better Blood brain barrier (BBB) interaction. However, this benefit must be balanced against potential safety concerns.^[20] The way a medicine is given plays a big role in how well liposomes

can deliver it to the brain. Intra-arterial delivery offers better targeting in specific regions compared to intravenous administration. It reduces overall exposure and increases accumulation in the brain. still, intravenous delivery is still the most generally used system in clinical settings because it's non-invasive and easy to administer.^[19]

3.2 Exosome

Exosomes are rapidly emerging as one of the most promising innovations in the administration of medications. These naturally occurring nanocarriers move complex natural molecules with extreme precision and minimal susceptibility through the body's fragile barriers, such as the BBB. They are a powerful response to many of the issues that the brain's present remedial delivery systems encounter because of their inherent comity with the mortal body, stability in rotation, and capacity for specific delivery.^[21] Their natural origin and nanoscale size, which ranges from 30 to 150 nm, enable efficient cellular uptake and systemic rotation while reducing immune clearance. Further, exosomes can target particular tissues thanks to face proteins like integrating and tetraspanins.^[22] Extracellular vesicles in the brain let cells communicate with one another. Their capability to cross the blood- brain barrier gives them an edge over traditional medicine delivery styles. They can target specific cells, carry remedial chemicals, and stay stable in the rotation.^[23] Exosome distribution is significantly told by their size, face parcels, and targeting tactics. When given systemically, exosomes can cross the blood- brain barrier and gather in brain tissue. Exosomes from colourful cell types show differing situations of brain magnet. Exosomes can be modified by altering their surface with ligands, antibodies, or peptides to increase target accuracy. They can now precisely target particular brain regions or cells thanks to this alteration. Exosomes are becoming recognized as efficient delivery systems for delivering nucleic acids to the brain.^[24] Exosomes can contain therapeutic nucleic acids, including antisense oligonucleotides, siRNA, miRNA, and then mRNA. Both external and natural loading techniques, which employ distinct chemical mechanisms, can be used for this method.^[25]

3.3 Polymeric nanoparticle

When it comes to delivering medications to the brain, polymeric nanoparticles provide unique advantages. They have several possibilities for altering their surface, can contain multiple medications at once, and provide exact control over how pharmaceuticals are delivered. Polylactic acid, polylactic-co-glycolic acid, and chitosan-based nanoparticles are the most studied polymeric systems.^[26] A key component of creating polymeric nanoparticles that can pass across the blood-brain barrier is altering their surface. Brain Immersion effectiveness is significantly increased by the addition of cell- piercing peptides, surfactants, and targeting ligands. A lot of exploration has been done on Polysorbate 80 coating. This entails apolipoprotein adsorption and commerce

with brain endothelial cells' low- viscosity lipoprotein receptor.^[27] particle size optimization is essential for effective brain delivery. According to studies, the nanoparticles for passing across the blood brain barrier without being cleared by the feathers are those that are between 10 and 200 nm in size. Transport effectiveness is also impacted by shape. Compared to other forms, globular patches frequently have superior cellular uptake.^[6]

3.4 Dendrimer

Dendrimer nanocarriers are a potential develop of nanoparticles that have the potential to penetrate the blood-brain barrier and deliver medications to the central nervous system. The BBB is a selective barrier that prevents the brain from receiving the best treatments. This makes treating neurological disorders extremely difficult. The structure of dendrimers is distinct, hyperactively fanned, and three-dimensional. This affords them unique benefits for brain targeting, such as a harmonious size, good facial functionality, and interior depressions that can contain inheritable accessories or coloured medication motes.^[28] Dendrimers containing polyamidoamines (PAMAM) are among the best in piercing the blood-brain barrier. When inserted into the carotid artery, mixed face PAMAM dendrimers which feature a mix of cationic and neutral groups have been shown to cross the blood-brain barrier in live things. Without damaging the tissue, they settle in glial and neuronal cells. They are effective carriers for delivering drugs, including RNA payloads and small compounds, to the brain because of their ability to pass across the corpus callosum and the blood-brain barrier.^[29] surface functionalization is a critical strategy for enhancing dendrimer mediated transport across the blood brain barrier. when dendrimer is coupled with specific targeting moieties, like transferrin, wheat germ agglutinin or bioactive peptides which promote receptor mediated transcytosis mechanism, the efficiency of brain absorption is significantly enhanced. Furthermore, dual ligand targeting dendrimers exhibit enhanced drug delivery efficacy and specificity to brain tumour cells, optimizing therapeutic intervention for malignant condition such as gliomas.^[30] Their nanoscale size prevents fast clearance while enabling paracellular and transcellular trafficking via endothelial cells. Furthermore, dendrimers can be engineered to have improved biocompatibility and reduced cytotoxicity, both of which are critical for clinical application.^[31] Increasing dendrimer synthesis, completely comprehending their toxicity, and guaranteeing focused delivery to the brain without compromising other organs, such as the liver and kidneys, remain difficult tasks despite promising experimental and clinical advancements. Further research focuses on improving dendrimer pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics, modifying surfaces with multiple targeting groups, and creating non-invasive method to deliver drugs safely and effectively to the Central nervous system drug delivery.^[32]

3.5 Biomimetic nanoparticles

Drug delivery vehicles called biomimetic nanoparticles (BNPs) imitate the membranes of real cells. They can more successfully penetrate the blood-brain barrier and target brain problems because to their architecture. Because these nanoparticles employ membrane coats from many cells, they are highly biocompatible, may evade the immune system, and have a longer half-life. This enhances the way treatments are delivered to the brain.^[33] Drug delivery vehicles called biomimetic nanoparticles (BNPs) mimic the membranes of real cells. They can more successfully penetrate the blood-brain barrier and target brain problems because to its structure. These nanoparticles make advantage of colourful cell membrane coatings. They've a longer rotation duration, are more biocompatible, and are suitable to shirk the vulnerable system because to this. These characteristics enhance the way treatments are delivered to the brain.^[34] BNPs have also been delved for the treatment of neurodegenerative ails including Parkinson's and Alzheimer's disease. They target poisonous proteins and neuroinflammation and aid in the passage of specifics over the blood- brain barrier. This system alters the course of the illness and encourages neurodegeneration. They use transcellular routes, endocytosis, and receptor-intermediated transport as part of their medium. As a report, they can pass through blood brain endothelial cells without injuring the barrier defence mechanisms.^[35] Furthermore, therapeutic applications that integrate targeted therapy and diagnosis can be developed using these biomimetic nanocarrier systems. This is evident in models of traumatic brain injury where nanoparticles provide imaging contrast and reduce inflammation. Biosafety, clinical translation, and obtaining regulatory permission for biomimetic nanoparticles utilized in brain disease therapy remain obstacles despite the great potential.^[36] Biomimetic nanoparticles have been shown to carry therapeutic agents that target key issues such as amyloid beta-aggregation, tau phosphorylation, α -synuclein accumulation, and neuroinflammation. For example, biomimetic nanocarrier loaded with curcumin and modified with targeting peptides showed improved dopamine recovery and protected neurons in Parkinson's disease models by inhibiting α -synuclein aggregation and oxidative stress. This active targeting improves drug availability in the brain and helps with neurodegeneration while reducing systemic side effects.^[37]

4. MECHANISM

4.1 Passive diffusion

One important mechanism by which certain small molecule medications enter the brain is passive diffusion over the blood-brain barrier. The physiochemical characteristics of the medication, especially its molecular weight and hydrogen-bonding capacity, are crucial to this process. A medication must typically have a molecular weight of less than 400 Daltons and create fewer than eight hydrogen bonds with water in order to pass through the blood-brain barrier (BBB) via lipid-mediated free

diffusion.^[38] Because of these stringent criteria, the majority of small-molecule medications and all big molecules are unable to passively diffuse across the blood-brain barrier. Tight connections on the special endothelial cells that make up the Blood brain barrier prevent cell-to-cell transfer. Other non-specific entrance points are also restricted by inadequate fluid-phase pinocytosis.^[39] Rather, chemicals need to dissolve in and flow through the lipid membranes of the Blood brain barrier endothelial cells. Because bigger molecules experience steric hindrance and decreased permeability across the lipid bilayer, there is a barrier for molecular weight. Lipid solubility and, thus, membrane permeability are reduced by hydrogen bonding. Lipidizing a drug molecule or other attempts to increase lipid solubility in order to promote passive diffusion frequently fail because of rapid in vivo hydrolysis or loss of pharmacological action.^[40] Consequently, small lipophilic molecules with less hydrogen bonding are preferred via passive diffusion. Since most drugs are not able to reach the brain through this technique, passive diffusion represents a significant but constrained method of drug entry. This emphasizes the necessity of alternative transporter-based medication delivery methods throughout the blood-brain barrier.^[41]

4.2 Carrier mediated mechanism

Carrier-mediated transport (CMT), which uses certain transporter proteins on endothelial cells, is a most important method for delivering drugs selectively across the blood-brain barrier.^[42] These transporters facilitate the absorption of essential nutrients such as amino acids and glucose. Drugs can improve their ability cross the blood-brain barrier if they share structural similarities with these nutrients. A number of carrier systems, including as amino acid transporters and organic cation transporters (OCTs), control the selective and saturated entry of small molecules into the brain. Carrier-mediated drug transport across the blood-brain barrier is characterized by competitive inhibition and a preference for similar natural substrate molecules.^[43] One potential way of delivering medications to the central nervous system is to take use of these transporters. This method overcomes the limits imposed by efflux transporters and enhances brain targeting. Improving Central nervous system bioavailability and developing novel treatments for neurological disorders depend on an understanding of and ability to use carrier-mediated transport mechanisms at the BBB.^[44]

4.3 Receptor-mediated transcytosis (RMT)

Through ligand-receptor interactions on the inner side of brain endothelial cells, a multi-step process known as receptor-mediated transcytosis (RMT) aids in the passage of large molecules across the blood-brain barrier. First, ligands such as growth factors, insulin, or transferrin attach to their respective luminal membrane receptors. Primarily through clathrin-coated pits, this binding triggers receptor-mediated endocytosis.^[45] The receptor-ligand complexes are consequently internalized into

vesicles. Following their merger with early endosomes, sorting determines the cargo's destiny. Molecules intended for brain delivery avoid lysosomal pathways by passing through sorting tubules and multivesicular bodies rather than being broken down. The therapeutic contents of these vesicles ultimately permeate the brain tissue via the abluminal membrane. This transcytosis mechanism enables the selective transport of crucial molecules and specially designed drugs while preserving the integrity of the BBB. Key receptors involved in this process include the insulin receptor (INSR), low-density lipoprotein receptors (LDLR, LRP1, LRP8), and the transferrin receptor. To create effective brain delivery systems, it is essential to comprehend the distinct trafficking and sorting properties of each receptor.^[46]

4.4 Adsorptive-Mediated Transcytosis (AMT)

Cationic substances, such as positively charged proteins or peptides, engage electrostatically with the negatively charged surfaces of endothelial cells in brain capillaries forming the blood-brain barrier via a mechanism termed adsorptive-mediated transcytosis (AMT). This interaction prompts the initiation of endocytosis. The molecules are transported across endothelial cells in vesicles before being released into the brain tissue.^[47] AMT enhances brain uptake through the use of cat ionized proteins or cell-penetrating peptides, maintaining the integrity of the BBB. The naturally charge-driven binding and vesicular transport mechanisms of the blood-brain barrier enable the efficient delivery of pharmacological agents. However, issues like toxicity and peptide stability persist. Consequently, Adsorptive Mediated Transcytosis provides a practical means of delivering medications to the CNS through electrostatic adsorption and intracellular vesicular transport mechanisms.^[48]

4.5 Efflux transporters

Efflux transporters play a crucial role in the blood-brain barrier, controlling the entry of drugs into the central nervous system by actively expelling different drugs from brain endothelial cells into the bloodstream. At the blood-brain barrier, membrane proteins known as efflux transporters actively remove various drugs and xenobiotics from the brain to prevent their entry into the CNS.^[49] These transporters, part of the ATP-binding cassette group and predominantly found on the luminal surface of brain capillary endothelial cells, comprise breast cancer resistance protein, multidrug resistance proteins, and P-glycoprotein.^[50] The efflux process is characterized by its energy requirement. It transfers materials from endothelial cells into the bloodstream by means of ATP hydrolysis. This process lessens the buildup of medications in the brain's interstitial space. This transporter's role creates an active barrier that works with tight junctions and the breakdown of enzymes to shield the brain from dangerous substances. Efflux transporters limit the entry of therapeutic drugs, which leads to treatment resistance in CNS diseases.^[51]

5. APPLICATION

5.1 Liposome

Liposomes are widely used and increasingly important as transporters for treating many brain disorders. They can be used to treat malignant brain tumours, stroke, epilepsy, migraines, autism, and paediatric central nervous system disorders in addition to Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disorder condition.^[52] Chemotherapy drugs delivered by modified liposomes can cross the blood-brain barrier to treat brain tumour. They have shown excellent targeted efficacy in models of paediatric brain tumours including glioblastoma. This includes doxorubicin and liposomal daunorubicin, which are FDA-approved formulations.^[53] In ischemic stroke studies, PEGylated and ligand-targeted liposomes containing neuroprotective substances such as a sialoerythropoietin or enzymes (SOD) have successfully concentrated in the injured region of the brain. This enhances neuronal survival and motor functions relative to unbound drugs.^[54] Liposomal nanocarriers also benefit Paediatric neurological disorders. They aid in the treatment of epilepsy, migraine, autism, and ADHD through the use of focused, low-toxicity therapies. This is especially the case when liposomes are engineered for oral, nasal, or intravenous administration and altered to enhance their ability to cross the blood brain barrier.^[55] Additionally novel liposome-based systems are enhancing gene therapy in the central nervous system. They provide therapeutic genes or monoclonal antibodies for inflammatory and Neurodegenerative diseases In vivo research demonstrates improved behavioural results an enhanced neuronal survival. Liposomes serve as imaging agent, diagnostic tools, and vehicles for transporting antiviral drugs to brain in CNS infectious diseases.^[56]

5.2 Exosome

Exosomes are attracting significant interest as natural nanocarriers for the treatment of brain disorders. This is because of their capability to traverse the BBB, their minimal immunogenic response, and their abundant presence of bioactive compounds.^[57]

Alzheimer's Disease: Exosome nanocarriers can transport nucleic acids (siRNA, miRNA) or treatments to reduce amyloid-beta accumulation and tau pathology. Genetically engineered exosomes that transport particular siRNAs have shown efficacy in animal models, reducing toxic protein accumulation and enhancing neuronal performance.^[58,59]

Stroke and Traumatic Brain Injury (TBI) Exosomes containing neurotrophic factors or anti-inflammatory miRNAs, like miR- 210 or mRNA, enhance neuron survival, enhance neurogenesis, reduce intravenous administration enable exosomes to access damaged regions and affect neuroinflammation, apoptosis, and angiogenesis. This results in improved cognitive and motor results.^[60]

Multiple Sclerosis (MS) and Neuroinflammation Exosome therapies in animal models of MS consist of administering anti-inflammatory composites, gene controllers, or nonsupervisory miRNAs that dwindle demyelination and influence vulnerable cell activity. Exosomes deduced from stem cells have demonstrated the capability to mend disruptions in the BBB and promote remyelination, supporting in the restoration of neural function.^[61]

Exosomes provide targeted chemotherapeutic delivery to glioma cells, bypassing the Blood brain barrier while reducing systemic toxicity. Surface-modified exosomes can increase targeting specificity to malignant tissue via ligand or antibody attachment. Preclinical results show effective tumour regression and fewer side effects compared to conventional delivery.^[62]

5.3 Polymeric nanoparticle

When various therapeutic drugs are administered continuously within a unified system, polymeric nanoparticles demonstrate remarkable effectiveness. By leveraging synergistic interactions, drugs with complementary action mechanisms can enhance overall effectiveness. In the combination of chemotherapy and radiotherapy, chemotherapeutic agents and radiation sensitizers are incorporated into nanodrugs to increase the sensitivity of tumour cells and improve treatment outcomes. To enhance the stability and absorption of medication, chemotherapy drugs such as doxorubicin, cisplatin, or TMZ can be encapsulated within nanodrugs.^[63] Alzheimer's Disease: Recent reviews describe how polymeric nanoparticles facilitate the passage of drugs through the BBB. This enables a more effective targeting of the fundamental issues associated with AD compared to conventional medications. Tailoring the surface charge and shape enhances targeting and boosts therapeutic effectiveness.^[64]

Parkinson's Disease: Nanocarriers simplify the delivery of levodopa, dopamine agonists, and neuroprotective drugs. Altering the surface permits targeting of specific BBB transporters, which increases the concentration of the drug in the central nervous system while minimizing systemic side effects. Polymeric nanoparticles facilitate the targeted delivery of chemotherapy drugs directly to brain tumours sites, successfully bypassing the BBB and minimizing harm to surrounding healthy tissues. Nanoparticles coated with ligands can selectively locate and transport drugs directly to cancer cells via receptor-mediated mechanisms.^[65]

5.4 Dendrimers

Dendrimers have become attractive nanocarriers for treating different brain disorders because their distinct branched structure permits precise regulation of size, surface chemistry, and drug loading, which facilitates efficient penetration of the blood-brain barrier.^[66] Generation 4 PAMAM dendrimers with hydroxyl terminal groups, attached to drugs like N-acetyl cysteine

(NAC) and valproic acid (VPA), have shown targeted delivery to damaged neurons and activated microglia in large animal models of brain injury. These dendrimer-drug conjugates diminish neuroinflammation and excitotoxicity, enhance neurological deficit scores, and yield therapeutic effects at roughly one-tenth the dosage of free drugs, greatly reducing side effects.^[30] Phosphorus dendrimers have been explored for Alzheimer's disease and neurodegeneration models because they can hinder amyloid fibril formation and encourage the disaggregation of current amyloid and tau aggregates, demonstrating neuroprotective potential.^[67] Additionally, PAMAM dendrimers containing antioxidants, anti-inflammatory compounds, or siRNA have effectively been absorbed selectively by activated microglia in animal models of cerebral palsy, leading to decreased neuroinflammation and enhanced motor performance.^[68] Different dendrimer varieties, like polypropylene mine (PPI) modified with transferrin or sialic acid, have shown improved BBB targeting in rodent glioma models, enhancing drug delivery and gene expression results. Dendrimer structures such as dendri-grafted poly-L-lysine (DGL) are also promising for concurrently targeting the blood brain barrier and tumours cells in animal models of brain cancer and neurodegenerative diseases, facilitating effective transfection and targeted treatment.^[69] In general, dendrimer nanocarriers enhance drug solubility, stability, and half-life while promoting selective uptake by brain cells; they decrease systemic toxicity via targeted delivery; and they support innovative drug and gene therapies across various neurological conditions. They are useful for neuroinflammatory injuries, neurodegenerative illnesses such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disorder, brain cancer, and cerebral ischemia.^[30]

5.5 Biomimetic nanoparticle

Nanoparticles coated with biomimetic cell membranes enhance drug delivery for neurodegenerative disorders such as Huntington's disorder, Parkinson's disorder, Alzheimer's disorder, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis by improving penetration through the blood-brain barrier and minimizing harmful immune reactions.^[33]

Brain Tumours and Brain Metastases: Nanoparticles enveloped in cancer cell membranes or hybrid membranes aim at the inflammatory BBB areas to accurately deliver anticancer drugs that inhibit tumours growth and metastasis in brain tumours.^[14]

Ischemic Stroke: Biomimetic nanoparticles coated with red blood cell membranes and stroke-targeting peptides aim to transport neuroprotective drugs that can cross the BBB, minimizing damage by eliminating reactive oxygen species (ROS) in ischemic brain areas.^[70] Parkinson's disease: Cell membrane-based biomimetic delivery devices enhance treatment by improving CNS medication delivery, minimizing side effects, and

managing pathological traits like neuroinflammation and protein aggregation.^[71]

6. LIMITATION AND CHALLENGE

Physical and biological obstacle: The blood-brain barrier is a selective barrier that prevents the most of drugs and nanocarriers from entering the central nervous system while also protecting the brain. It consists of pericytes, astrocytes, and then endothelial cells that are tightly connection. **Stability and drug release management:** Nanocarriers continue to face challenges in delivering the medication in a regulated manner, preventing renal clearance, and maintaining stability in the bloodstream.^[72]

Restricted targeting effectiveness and penetration: Nanocarriers often struggle to effectively accumulate in the brain target area and penetrate adequately, thereby reducing treatment efficacy. **Peripheral circulation and immune elimination:** Nanocarriers have a brief duration in the bloodstream and are rapidly removed by the immune system, restricting their ability to cross the BBB.^[73]

Toxicity concerns: Nanoparticles may lead to inflammation, neuronal injury, or irreversible cell death if not carefully constructed, making systemic toxicity (from off-target effects) and neurotoxicity (affecting brain tissues) significant challenges.^[74]

Variability in Barriers Specific to Disease: Drug penetration and the properties of the BBB may differ based on the medical condition. Drug delivery outcomes can often be influenced, sometimes unpredictably, by disruptions or irregularities in the integrity of the BBB during disease.

Low permeability and drug delivery efficiency: A frequent issue for neonatal patients is low permeability through the BBB. Only a small percentage (3–5%) of brain-targeted medications achieve therapeutic levels. The limited penetration is largely attributed to the BBB's selective permeability and active efflux mechanisms, like P-glycoprotein, that expel foreign substances.^[75]

7. FUTURE ASPECTS

The future of nanocarrier research for the blood–brain barrier (BBB) looks bright, as advancements focus on addressing existing challenges in delivering drugs specifically to the brain. Future directions involve engineering nanocarriers with improved specificity, stability, and BBB penetration through optimized surface modifications and employing biomimetic designs to enhance compatibility and evade the immune system. The research will also focus the integrating various targeting methods, including dual-ligand strategies, to enhance treatment effectiveness for complex neurological conditions such as Parkinson's disorder, Alzheimer's disorder, and brain tumours. Moreover, future advance developments will address regulatory and

safety issues related to nanotoxicity and off-target impacts, creating opportunities for the clinical application of groundbreaking treatments and the growth of integrated diagnostic and therapeutic application tailored to the specific requirements of patients.

8. CONCLUSION

The blood-brain barrier remains an important barrier to treating neurological conditions because it is so selective and prevents most therapeutic medications from getting into the brain. Nanocarriers such liposomes, exosomes, polymeric nanoparticles, dendrimers, and biomimetic nanoparticles have emerged as promising alternatives due to their customized delivery and improved BBB penetration. To allow to overcome the BBB's limitations and treat conditions like Parkinson's and Alzheimer's, brain tumours, and strokes, these systems employ a number of mechanisms, including receptor-mediated transcytosis, adsorptive mediated transcytosis, carrier mediated transport, and passive diffusion. However, there are still significant challenges, such as immune clearance, instability, limited targeted efficacy, and potential neurotoxicity. Enhancing the safety, specificity, and efficacy of nanocarriers is crucial for enabling the clinical translation of the most advanced therapies and enhancing patient outcomes in the central nervous system.

9. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors are thankful to The Erode College of Pharmacy, Erode (Tamil Nadu, India) for providing the necessary facilities to carry out this work. The authors also express their sincere gratitude to Mrs. S. Vanitha, Associate Professor, Department of Pharmaceutics, for her valuable guidance and constant support during the preparation of this manuscript. The cooperation of faculty members, library staffs is gratefully acknowledged.

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